

ANNUAL REPORT 2018

Implementation - Transforming the
Norwegian Biotech Landscape

«Bacteria - the New Superheroes»

CREDITS

Published by:
Centre for Digital Life Norway

Design:
NTNU Grafisk Senter

Illustration:
Renate Thor

TABLE OF CONTENTS

From the Centre Leader	5
Comments from the board	7
The Centre for Digital Life research projects	8
Five new research projects	17
The Digital Life Norway Portfolio	20
Bringing forward synergies in Digital Life Norway - Collaborations between research projects	21
Managing our research data	22
Planning together – The Selbu Search Conference	24
Innovation for future biotech	26
Digital Life 2018 – Two days of knowledge sharing	28
Inreach and outreach activities	29
The 2nd annual conference of Digital Life Norway research school	30
Sparkling a scientific career in the centre for Digital Life	31
The Digital Life Year at a Glance	32
New Board Members and Coordinators	35

FROM THE CENTRE LEADER

Dear all!

After three years running, Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN) has gradually become a weighty player within transdisciplinary biotechnology in Norway. In December 2018, we welcomed five new research projects originating in four different institutions, including Oslo University Hospital as one new institutional partner node.

Fundamental to the entire organization of the Centre is collaboration across traditional boundaries. In total, DLN now hosts 26 research projects including partner projects and seven institutional partners. We are starting to reap the fruits of the synergy efforts we have carefully laid the groundwork for, and continuously facilitated, from the very beginning of our operation. One such example is the workshop arranged by two of our research projects, addressing the major global challenge of antibiotic resistance, that included international speakers and patients' organizations.

We experience that DLN is consolidating Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) as an increasingly relevant and manageable concept. The leading competence the DLN holds within RRI was materialized in a unique research school course addressing RRI in particular. A thoroughly planned and executed course sparked engaged discussions and unveiled research school members with national talents on the topic.

DLN has reached a point where we are starting to see tangible results of the entire initiative. The Centre has become a substantial platform for research, training and innovation, and we also provide a unifying voice for decision makers in matters like data management, open science, and large infrastructure. A major event in 2018 was the DLN Search Conference in Selbu. Project leaders, centre leaders and coordinators, as well as others holding central roles spent two days together to discuss current status and further priorities for the

Centre. This converted into a report describing priorities and actions necessary to fulfill our mandate, and more so, to strengthen and bring our centre to the next level.

In 2019 we will implement the results from the Search Conference and take advantage of the current strong momentum to develop the Centre into a lighthouse for Norwegian biotechnology.

Trygve Brautaset, Centre Leader

COMMENTS FROM THE BOARD

The third year of operation of Digital Life Norway (DLN) has appropriately been labelled «Implementation – changing the Norwegian biotech landscape». DLN is a rather unique project for two main reasons: 1) DLN has established a platform for solid and trustful collaboration across institutional boundaries, and 2) In DLN, there is a continuous dialogue with the Research Council of Norway (RCN) regarding the direction and stewardship of the center.

In January, DLN presented its view on how to best tailor the last call for funding from RCN to the program board of Biotek2021 to achieve the objectives of the center. When the call came, I was happy to see that the program board agreed with the center and near the end of the year, we welcomed five new research projects as part of DLN. Importantly, in addition to a call for more research projects, considerable funding from RCN was dedicated a targeted call for strengthening the innovation activities (deadline for this application was in April 2019). One of the five new research projects is hosted by Oslo University Hospital, expanding the DLN family with one more institution.

In 2018 there were two changes in the board membership. UiT rotated in for NMBU as node representative. However, the Board unanimously agreed that nodes not represented on the Board should be able to have an observer present at all meetings, so for practical purposes this was an expansion rather than an exchange. We welcome Arne Smalås, Dean of the Faculty of Science and Technology at UiT as node-representative board member. We also welcome new member from industry, Emilie Lasson, Chief Commercial Officer, Genetic Analysis AS.

The Board is very pleased with the development of DLN. We are impressed by how the DLN Network Project and research projects are changing the national biotechnology research landscape, particularly

in the area of collaboration across institutions and transdisciplinary research. When the forthcoming «innovation package» from RCN comes into action, we trust that links to industry and innovation activities will grow even stronger. The collaborative spirit of the work package coordinators and leaders in the network project has rubbed off on the board members. Board meetings are thus a venue for fruitful discussions about best practice and stewardship of DLN. As detailed elsewhere in this annual report, the Selbu Conference was a major event in 2018. The Board is still digesting the outcome of the conference and looking forward to implement measures that were suggested. We are also looking forward to the self-assessment that the RCN will organize with the center in 2019. We are confident that 2019 will be another exciting and good year for DLN.

On behalf of the Board,

Finn-Eirik Johansen, Chair

THE CENTRE FOR DIGITAL LIFE RESEARCH PROJECTS

Credit: Øystein Arlov and Hanne Haslene-Hox, Sintef

3DLIFE

Commonly used cellular monolayer cultures are remote reflections of in vivo conditions, due to a lack of the cellular, structural and chemical elements forming the tissue microenvironment. 3DLife aims to develop novel strategies for microtissue engineering in 3D, to provide model systems of organ function and bridge the gap to in vivo conditions. This is relevant for studying tissue biology and disease, and for testing pharmaceutical and toxic compounds.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

In the first part of the project we have focused on tailoring the mechanical and biological properties in the tissue constructs. We have started making a library of alginate-based materials and developed methods for robotic screening system in 3D hydrogels. We have also worked on other cell types than fibroblasts, which is the primary focus in the project, to expand the usability of the platform. The project concept has been communicated in radio, podcast and at conferences.

AHA! ADAPTIVE HEURISTICS AND ARCHITECTURE

AHA! aims to develop a modularized general model of a population of animals with adapted behavioral architecture to support decision-making, expose it to standard ecological scenarios, and use the model animal and environment to test the importance of each module for the emergence of behavioral strategies, personality types, and physiological/behavioral syndromes.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

A paper describing the model is published (Budaev & al 2018), another is accepted (Budaev & al 2019).
Budaev S, Giske J, Eliassen S 2018. AHA: a general cognitive architecture for Darwinian agents. *Biologically Inspired Cognitive Architectures*. 25: 51-57
Budaev S, Jørgensen C, Mangel M, Eliassen S, Giske J 2019. Decision-making from the animal perspective: Bridging ecology and subjective cognition. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*.

Thraustochytrid cultivations in bench-top bioreactors. The biomass can contain over 70% lipids at the end of the cultivation. The red colour stems from a minor side production of carotenoids. MSc Gunn Broli. Photo: SINTEF.

AUROMEGA

The primary objective of AurOmega is to establish a knowledge platform on DHA synthesis and lipid accumulation in native DHA-producing thraustochytrids, and to develop these into high productivity omega-3 fatty acid producing cell factories. Thraustochytrids can be cultivated at high cell concentration and are extremely promising microorganisms for development of economic competitive production processes for omega-3 fatty acids.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

First year of operation has centered around adjustment of omics protocols for this high-lipid system. A first draft of a thraustochytrids genome-scale metabolic model has been finished. Thus, we are ready for system-levels studies, and the first metabolome and proteome data have provided new and interesting information on DHA synthesis. We arranged a workshop discussing how GMO-produced omega-3 fatty acids be acceptable as fish feed ingredients.

BEDPAN*

In BEDPAN we are engineering bacterial strains to produce fine-tuned palladium nanoparticles with specific sizes and shapes. This method offers a more environmentally friendly alternative to the currently used chemical and physical methods that involve toxic and expensive chemical agents. Our strains will produce novel materials that can be used in medical applications, electronics, energy cells, and as catalysts for many chemical industries.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

Palladium nanoparticles formation process by bacteria was previously carried out under anaerobic conditions. In 2018, we were able to change some conditions to make it happen under aerobic conditions. Moreover, we identified some genes and pathways involved in this unknown process. The deregulation of these genes and pathways resulted in different nanoparticles properties.

* The BEDPAN project moved from being a partner project of the Centre, to a BIOTEK21-funded project in 2018.

BIGINSIGHT

Electronic health records at patient level are time series or time processes of very varying types. Time series of the medical and nursing work in the ward are also available, together with external factors like air humidity and temperature. We have developed a new method, which is able to select which of these input time series affect most the output, namely a measure of the risk of hospital acquired infections (HAI). The method has been tested on simulated data very successfully.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

How does urbanisation effect the spread of epidemics? We proposed a method for generating spatial fields with controllable levels of clustering of the population. We build a synthetic country, and use this method to generate versions of the country with different clustering levels. Combined with a metapopulation model for infectious disease spread, this allows us to explore in silico how urbanisation affects infectious disease spread, and to examine effectiveness of prevention measures as a function of urbanisation.

BIOZEMENT 2.0

Globally, concrete production accounts for more than 5% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. This project aims to develop a sustainable bio-concrete material based on bacterially induced dissolution and precipitation of CaCO₃. Systems biology metabolic modelling, advanced microbiological techniques, material characterization, and geochemical reactive transport simulations are combined in order to optimize the system. We also consider environmental and consumer aspects that may affect the future use of the product.

CaCO₃ crystal with imprints of bacteria.
Photo: Jennifer Zehner.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

The project has progressed according to plan in modelling activities, experimental setup and strain development. We have conducted and analysed results from focus groups and received additional funding for prototype development. Outputs have been one scientific publication, two submitted manuscripts, ten conference contributions, decision to continue patent application process in three selected regions, two podcast appearances, a presentation at industry-science meetup, a contribution at panel debate at Arendalsuka, a presentation at open day for high school students, and an interview in energiogklima.no.

Minister of Higher Education Iselin Nybø meets dCod 1.0 at Arendalsuka 2018. Dorothy Dankel, Karina Dale and Siri Øfsthus Goksøyr makes sure she gets it. Photo: Solfrid Langeland, UiB

DCOD 1.0

The goal of the dCod-project is to combine the competencies in environmental toxicology, biology, bioinformatics and mathematics across the traditional department boundaries, to create a deeper understanding of cods' adaptations and reactions to stressors in the environment. The projects aims to generate large amounts of experimental data to be the basis of mathematical models that can describe these responses based on different scenarios. Furthermore, the overall goal is to create tools for environmental monitoring and risk assessment that can be used in assessing the impacts of for example the oil industry, sewage discharge into harbours and industrial discharge into Norwegian fjords.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

The dCod 1.0 Winter Workshop 2018 (Skjelbreid-Poiree Lodge, Fusa) January 8-9, 26 participants, including guests Dan Zielinsky from UCSD and Jon Olav Vik from DigiSal. Workshops and seminars around data management and FAIRDOM, biweekly project meetings, and presentation of the project at several conferences. Outreach/RRRI highlight: Arendalsuka 2018. Publication highlight: Loss of PXR-paper in Scientific Reports: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-018-28498-4>

DOUBLE INTRAPERITONEAL ARTIFICIAL PANCREAS

The goal of the Double Intraperitoneal Artificial Pancreas (DIAP) project is to create a robust fully automatic solution for insulin delivery in patients with diabetes. This should normalize or close to normalize the glucose levels. To achieve this we aim at measuring glucose and deliver insulin in the peritoneal space. Our solution will need the development of an abdominal port, new technology for intraperitoneal glucose sensing as well as new algorithms for steering of insulin delivery.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

In 2018 we published «Effect of sensor location on continuous intraperitoneal glucose sensing in an animal model» with Marte K. Åm as first author. This paper was also awarded the Centre for Digital Life Norway's Transdisciplinary Publication of the Year. Another land mark was the paper «Intraperitoneal, subcutaneous and intravenous glucagon delivery and subsequent glucose response in rats: A randomized controlled crossover trial» by Ilze Dirnena-Fusini, et.al. The paper identifies the possibility to add intraperitoneal glucagon to improve glucose control.

Computer simulation of an antimicrobial peptide entering a bacterial membrane. Image: Bjørn Olav Brandsdal.

DIGIBIOTICS

Antimicrobial resistance is currently causing around 700 000 deaths annually, with an estimated rise to 10 million over the next 30 years. DigiBiotics meets this challenge by exploring new compounds inspired by Arctic marine products and developing novel experimental and computational methods for determining molecular structure and dynamics, and interplay with bacteria. This will allow for a better understanding of drug-target interactions and provide an atomic resolution for drug development against novel targets.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

The focus of the first year was to establish the work-packages, develop methods, purchase equipment, and hire personnel. By the end of 2018, these goals are accomplished. DigiBiotics has been very active within RRI and elected the Norwegian Cancer Society as a representative for a patient group. Together with the INBioPharm project we arranged a one-day workshop "Ensuring new antibiotics for the future" for scientists and decisionmakers in Trondheim, attracting nearly 100 attendants.

DIGIBRAIN

Brain related disorders and disease are among the largest health challenges in the world today and will only increase with an aging population. Our current understanding of underlying mechanisms of brain disorders is limited. In DigiBrain, transdisciplinary researchers study mechanisms of disease in the brain and how these are coupled to different gene variants in patients. This knowledge can contribute to development of new drugs and novel treatments of patients with schizophrenia or bipolar disorder.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

The DigiBrain project is progressing as planned and has met all of the targeted milestones. Each WorkPackage continues to develop and corresponding articles have been published in scientific journals throughout 2018. We continue to contribute to public dissemination of our research, and the project sponsored the Mental Health and Addiction annual conference in Oslo in July. Three PIs from the project spoke at the event. A DigiBrain project workshop was also held in May to achieve a greater understanding of each other's interdisciplinary work.

Can we compute what to feed farmed salmon? Photo: J. O. Vik, K. Løwe, T. M. Austad.

DIGITAL SALMON

The Digital Salmon develops digital twins for farmed salmon. Computer simulations of the key life processes let us critically assess whether reality agrees with our understanding of salmon biology, enabling faster response to industry challenges. This heralds the era of digital production biology: integrating vast data in a systems understanding, building a shared knowledge base that is continually improving and growing in predictive power.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

This year we engaged industry players outside the original DigiSal consortium, first in a well-received talk at the Tekna aquaculture conference in Trondheim, then in organizing the first Digital Salmon industry workshop, which will take place in 2019. The project also published four papers, gave ten invited talks, and was cited in the government's long-term plan for research.

FUTURE ANTIBIOTICS

There is an urgent need for new antibiotics. Potential targets for antibiotics are riboswitches. We are using a structure-based approach to target the FMN and SAM riboswitches. Currently, we are working to obtain a crystal structure of a hit in complex with the FMN riboswitch to elucidate its binding mode. In addition, several analogues of the hit have been synthesized with the goal to improve affinity and to map interaction hot spots in the binding site. An improved assay for compound characterization is under development.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

The key highlight in 2018 was the synthesis of a number of derivatives of the screening hit.

Strains of the Actinobacteria strain collection at SINTEF/NTNU that serves as the basis for establishing the INBioPharm biodiscovery platform. Photo: Espen Fjærvik.

INBIOPHARM

The INBioPharm project develops an innovative platform for the more efficient discovery of novel antimicrobial drugs. A large strain collection of Actinobacteria collected from the Trondheim fjord is used as the starting point. New bioinformatics, cloning, synthetic biology and screening tools are combined to find and express promising biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) from these strains and characterize new bioactive compounds encoded in these.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

In 2018, new cloning technology has been implemented, in collaboration with Varigen Biosciences, and used to clone the first set of Actinobacteria BGCs. A new set of morphology and precursor supply improved expression strains of *S. coelicolor*, developed in ERASysAPP project SYSTERACT, has been validated. The first scientific full paper has been published, and the first public workshop has been arranged in collaboration with DLN project DigiBiotics.

This picture was originally published in the Journal of Biological Chemistry. Courtade G, Forsberg Z, Heggset EB, Eijsink VGH, Aachmann FL; The carbohydrate-binding module and linker of a modular lytic polysaccharide monooxygenase promote localized cellulose oxidation; J. Biol. Chem. 2018; 293:13006-13015. © the Authors.

OXYMOD

OXYMOD aims at discovering, understanding and applying redox enzyme systems for the conversion of biomass such as lignocellulose into valuable products. OXYMOD combines life sciences (enzyme technology, microbial biotechnology, high throughput screening, advanced analytics), bioinformatics (big data, enzyme systems modelling, process modelling) and engineering (enzyme evolution, synthetic biology) for developing novel biocatalytic systems.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

Studies of 1000 marine Actinomycete genomes have yielded a rich list of candidate redox enzymes, which are produced, partly using new technologies, and characterized. In 2018, we have obtained and published detailed structural and kinetic insights into some of these enzymes. Furthermore, we have initiated modelling of both kinetics, structural dynamics and catalysis for individual enzymes, and made our first steps towards kinetic modelling of enzyme systems.

Photo: Jens Høvik

LAB-ON-A-CHIP

Early detection of diseases dramatically increases the chance for successful treatment. The goal of the lab-on-a-chip biophotonic platform project is to develop a label-free platform to perform highly sensitive and selective quantitative diagnostic tests. The target is to measure different biomarkers in parallel in <20 min. This enables numerous biomedical applications such as diagnosis of infectious diseases and potentially cancer. Project manager is prof. Astrid Aksnes at the Dept. of Electronic Systems, NTNU.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

Single and multiple channel prototypes containing different waveguide-based sensing elements and microfluidic channels have been fabricated and tested. The sensing elements are surface functionalized to capture specific biomarkers. Physiologically relevant concentrations of the biomarker C-reactive protein were measured on the LOC prototype showing promising results. In 2018 results were presented at the international conferences Biosensors 2018, OSA Advanced Photonics Congress, and SPIE Optics & Photonics.

PERCATHE

PERCATHE develops new, powerful methods to build an innovative and practicable pipeline for individualised precision treatment of cancer, in particular breast and lung cancers and B cell malignancies.

The idea is to inform ex-vivo drug sensitivity testing of cancer patients' cells with a combination of drug synergy predictions, mathematical models of cancer multiscale and multitemporal processes, and patient based inference of cancer characterising parameters, exploiting medical imaging and genomics.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

We developed a comprehensive approach to model and simulate a breast tumor treated by two different chemotherapies in combination or not. We implemented a computer system which simulates a cross-section of the tumor under a 12 weeks therapy regimen. We showed how the model is able to reproduce patients from a clinical trial of OUS, both responders and not. We show that other drug regimens might have led to a different outcome. We were also able to correctly predict the outcome of one breast cancer patient.

RES PUBLICA

Res Publica is a concomitant research project to the Centre for Digital Life (DLN) with a focus on investigating social responsibility. Departing from DLN and its research projects, we map social responsibility questions in the socio-economic-political context of the Research Centre. As part of our research, we introduce action research methods to engage DLN and related actors in a learning process.

2018 Key Highlights for the Project

In 2018, Res Publica had its kick off meeting and conducted a screening activity of DLN-projects. We identified difficulties in implementing DLN's strategic initiative. Therefore, we initiated a search conference for organizational learning. Additionally, we decided to study further the Norwegian digital bioeconomy, the political-economy of aquaculture, and regulations concerning marine biodiversity. We also held a successful Responsible Research and Innovation-course for PhD candidates.

FIVE NEW RESEARCH PROJECTS - AN EXPERIMENT GROWING SIGNIFICANTLY

The third Digital Life call was realized in 2018, granting the Centre five new research projects.

– We started out with six projects, then we got twelve and now adding these five makes 17 altogether, along with the eight partner projects we have, counts Centre Leader Trygve Brautaset.

That there would be a third round of funding was not given from the start. – As the Centre is growing significantly its community is becoming large enough to contribute positively to synergies within the Centre. We may now fully collect the increment value of research being organized in this type of centre structure.

Brautaset thinks the Norwegian Research Council was future-oriented when establishing the Centre for Digital Life Norway. He also thinks the latest round of funding points forward within the research fields.

With the new projects the Centre is also strengthened with a new partner institution: Oslo University Hospital.

PIPELINE FOR INDIVIDUALLY TAILORING NEW TREATMENTS IN HAEMATOLOGICAL CANCERS

The project aims at predicting where efforts in screening and testing of cancer medications should be concentrated.

– Our research seeks to understand and develop molecular diagnostics, so that, by the use of gene analyses and testing of cancer medication directly on the patient cells, we can collect all data and use them to predict what would be the best treatment or the best combination of medications for each individual patient. It is not possible to test everything and we need computational approaches to predict what will work the best, explains project leader Kjetil Taskén, of the Oslo University Hospital.

In addition to Taskén, the leader group consists of Arnaldo Frigessi from the University of Oslo and Jorrit Enserink, also from Oslo University Hospital. Taskén estimates that around hundred researchers will be tied to the project in one way or the other, through the group leaders' various research groups and international and national partners.

RESPONSIBLE DIGITAL DRUG DISCOVERY

Professor Nathalie Reuter from the University of Bergen is the project leader of one of the other new projects to the Centre for Digital Life. Together with her colleagues Ruth Brenk, Bengt Erik Haug and Alexander Lundervold, she seeks to develop new types of antibiotics and medications for the lung disease Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) in the project: Towards better computational approaches and responsible innovation strategies in early drug discovery-application to antibiotics and COPD.

– We are adopting machine learning methods and wish to develop computational methods enabling us to speed up parts of the discovery process. The two cases are at different stages of the long term research, but they have in common that the most promising pharmaceutical candidates cannot be published. In our transdisciplinary team of researchers we are trying to identify in which phases we can take measures to reduce the gap between academia and the pharmaceutical industry in a way that takes care of the different needs, says Reuter.

She is looking forward to leading the project based out of Bergen. – This grants us good access to resources both within computational and experimental methods, as well as systemized work on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).

BIO-ENGINEERED PALLADIUM NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles of precious metal is used more and more in anything from optics, bio-medicine, car industry, to chemical catalysis. This project, lead by Dirk Linke at the University of Oslo, aims to use an environmentally friendly approach to produce nanoparticles, namely through the use of bacteria.

The goal is to establish production processes for nanoparticles of precious metal with tailored features for different areas of application, such as medical equipment, electronics, energy cells, and as catalysts for many chemical industries.

«LISTENING TO THE PATIENTS» – ANALYSIS OF BODY SOUNDS FOR DIAGNOSTICS AND MONITORING

The project aims to investigate whether it is possible to use registration of sound and advanced sound treatment to detect intake of food in patients with Diabetes Mellitus Type 1. Project leader is Sven M. Carlsen from NTNU, and his group's motive is to study whether this may be used as a method to detect food intake quicker than by the measurement of glucose continuously. If such is the case, the approach will be used in creating an artificial pancreas, that is a fully automatic control of insulin supply with patients with Diabetes Mellitus Type 1. Another aim is to study whether registration of sounds may be used when diagnosing and controlling various other diseases, especially those frequent to Diabetes Mellitus type 1 patients.

PROVIZ: PROSTATE CANCER VISUALIZATION BY MRI – IMPROVED DIAGNOSTICS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Prostate cancer is the most common type of cancer among Norwegian men. A standardized course for treatment of prostate cancer was established by Norwegian health authorities in 2015. This entails that when prostate cancer is suspected, based on PSA value and examination by a doctor, all men will receive an MR examination as the first part of the investigation by the specialist health service. The purpose with this project, lead by Tone Frost Bathen at NTNU, is to develop data tools based on artificial intelligence to analyze the MR pictures. This will give a quicker and more precise diagnose, which will further lead to better follow-up, treatment and life quality for the patients.

THE DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY PORTFOLIO

RESEARCH PROJECTS

- » **3DLife** – Emulating life in 3D with digital and experimental tissue models *(PI: Berit Løkenstrand)*
- » **Auromega** – Microbial production of omega-3 fatty acids - a model based approach *(PI: Per Bruheim, NTNU)*
- » **BEDPAN** – Bio-engineered palladium nanoparticles *(PI: Dirk Linke, UiO)*
- » **BioZement 2.0** – Systems analysis and fundamental control of bacterial processes in the production of bio-concrete for construction purposes *(PI: Anja Røyne, UiO)*
- » **dCod 1.0** – Decoding Systems Toxicology of Atlantic Cod *(PI: Anders Goksøy, UiB)*
- » **DigiBiotics** – Digital discovery of antimicrobial molecules from marine Arctic resources with reduced risk of triggering resistance *(PI: John-Sigurd Mjæen Svendsen, UiT)*
- » **DigiBrain** – From genes to brain function in health and disease *(PI: Marianne Fyhn, UiO)*
- » **Digital Salmon** – From a reactive to a pre-emptive research strategy in aquaculture *(PI: Jon Olav Vik, NMBU)*
- » **Double Intraperitoneal Artificial Pancreas** – An easier life with diabetes *(PI: Sven Magnus Carlsen, NTNU)*
- » **INBioPharm** – Integrated Novel Natural Product Discovery and Production Platform for Accelerated Biopharmaceutical Innovation from Microbial Biodiversity *(PI: Alexander Wentzel, SINTEF)*
- » **Lab-on-a-chip** – Biophotonic sensor platform for diagnostics *(PI: Astrid Aksnes, NTNU)*
- » **Listening to the Patients** – Analysis of body sounds for diagnostics and monitoring *(PI: Sven Magnus Carlsen, NTNU)*
- » **OXYMOD** – Optimized oxidative enzyme systems for efficient conversion of lignocellulose to valuable products *(PI: Vincent Eijsink, NMBU)*
- » **PerCaThe** – Pipeline for individually tailoring new treatments in haematological cancers *(PIs: Arnaldo Frigessi/Kjetil Taskén/Jorrit Enserink, UiO/OUS)*
- » **PROVIZ** – Prostate cancer visualization by MRI – Improved diagnostics using artificial intelligence *(PI: Tone Frost Bathen, NTNU)*
- » **RESPOND** – Towards better computational approaches and responsible innovation strategies in early drug discovery – application to antibiotics and COPD *(PI: Nathalie Reuter, UiB)*
- » **Res Publica** – Responsibility, practice and the public good across Digital Life *(PI: Heidrun Åm, NTNU)*

PARTNER PROJECTS

- » **Aha!** – Adaptive Heuristics and Architecture *(PI: Jarl Giske, UiB)*
- » **BigInsight** – Big insight from big data *(PI: Arnaldo Frigessi, UiO)*
- » **CCBIO** – Centre for Cancer Biomarkers *(PI: Lars A. Akslen, UiB)*
- » **DrugLogics** – Combinatorial drug treatment for cancer *(PI: Astrid Lægreid, NTNU)*
- » **Future Antibiotics** – To discover and optimize new antibiotics *(PI: Ruth Brenk, UiB)*
- » **ParkOme** – A database to understand Parkinson's disease *(PI: Charalampos Tzoulls, UiB)*

BRINGING FORWARD SYNERGIES IN DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY - COLLABORATIONS BETWEEN RESEARCH PROJECTS

The Centre offers funding to support activities between Digital Life Norway (DLN) research projects – so called «cross-project activities». In total, seven such activities were granted funding in 2018. This is one of the advantages of the DLN organization: the possibility of gained synergies, that would not have evolved from isolated research projects.

MANAGING OUR RESEARCH DATA

The FAIR principles continue to be an underlying principle of data management in Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN). Towards this aim, the Centre organizes data management workshops with practical training. We have supported the development of data management tools at infrastructure and project levels and we have started a community forum within the Centre, for those responsible for data management in the research projects.

During 2017 and 2018, DLN supported an integration of the Norwegian ELIXIR infrastructure, [NeLS](#) (Norwegian e-infrastructure for Life Sciences) with the much used SEEK platform from [FAIRDOM](#). The new releases make FAIR data management and long-term storage for Norwegian project leaders and collaborators easier. Several Digital Life projects; DigiSal, dCod 1.0, INBioPharm and BioZement 2.0, participated in the testing of the integrated platforms.

To initiate a data management community in DLN we had an advanced data management workshop at Gardermoen, where different tools were discussed together with data management activities in the participating research projects. We recommend more research projects to participate actively in our data management community through their data management responsible. Later in 2018 we organised

a two-day workshop together with FAIRDOM, NeLS and the DigiBrain project, where all interested could participate. This workshop covered both basic and advanced data management of the SEEK and NeLS platforms together with the integration features. In addition, DigiBrain had training using their data management tool Exdir, a novel and open specification for data storage in experimental pipelines.

The DLN networking project presented ongoing activities on data management on several international events, such as the "Data Management for Human Genomics" workshop in Uppsala, organized by SciLifeLab Data Centre; the FAIRDOM satellite meeting for the ICSB 2018 conference in Lyon; the NETTAB 2018 meeting in Genova, «Building a FAIR Bioinformatics environment».

During 2019, the centre is strengthening its resources on data management through a full data manager position, joined with ELIXIR Norway. With many new health related projects, the issue of sensitive data has become much more relevant in DLN. This will have increased focus in our work with data management during 2019.

PLANNING TOGETHER – THE SELBU SEARCH CONFERENCE

Digital Life's mandate is to create economic, societal and environmental value for Norway from biotechnological research and innovation through encouraging transdisciplinary research. Since its inception, DLN has steadily grown in terms of activities, research projects – Digital Life-funded as well as affiliated projects – and geographical spread. DLN has become a broad community for research, training and innovation. DLN has a broad scientific portfolio, and the organization is complex and distributed; hence a collective action to define common needs and future directions was necessary. This is why DLN gathered in Selbu on 14-15 November, 2018 for a so-called search conference. Among the 32 participants were leaders of DLN research projects (including partner projects), members of the DLN research school board, selected young scientists, and centre leaders and coordinators. The stated aim of the search conference was for participants to identify concrete priorities and steps that are needed to fulfil the mandate of DLN, which are then to be used in shaping DLN's action plan for 2019–2021.

A search conference is an internationally recognized method to facilitate long-term strategic thinking, learning and change in organizations. The methodology leads the participants through iterative group and plenary sessions with the goal of achieving consensus on the organization's priorities and matching activities to realize them. The discussions progress in a funnel-like process, starting from taking stock of an organization's environment to eventually narrowing down on concrete activities to be implemented. Each group work session builds and depends on the results of the previous sessions. In this manner, the search conference functions as an arrangement for reflexivity, anticipation and responsiveness, which are core elements of responsible research and innovation.

Figure 1: the session topics leading up to the activity plan

Photo: Raffael Himmelsbach

For two days, the participants worked in an incredibly focused manner. The following seven points summarize the key outcomes of these discussions. While they build on the Digital Life's achievements to date, their purpose is to point out future areas of action; and should not be read as an evaluation.

1. Digital Life builds on the "innovation through convergence" vision, meaning that when physical, biological, mathematical and engineering disciplines work together in biotechnology, new advances are possible that create social and economic benefits. The process of implementing this vision requires that we clarify its meaning and continue to develop it in the context of Digital Life.
2. One Digital Life research project can benefit from another's expertise and instruments; a good flow of information about respective competencies is essential.
3. The "Innovation through convergence" vision requires changes in how research, education and innovation are organized. Digital Life initiative's success critically depends on these changes also being taken up in the institutions of Norway's higher education, research and innovation system.
4. Digital Life's capability to partake in societal and political debate with a collective voice should be further strengthened.

5. There is a clear wish for the Centre to further strengthen its role in career development and transdisciplinary education, for PhD candidates as well as on post-doctors.
6. A societally responsible culture for innovation is a work in progress and will benefit from better integrating industrial partners.
7. DLN should continue to reach out to sister institutions abroad to establish new scientific cooperations and exchange experiences on making transdisciplinarity work.

We thank the Res Publica project for suggesting the search conference as a methodology. The event was organized by the RRI-team together with the rest of the governance workgroup and supported by Nicole Njå (AFF). We thank all the participants for their hard work and dedication during the event. The output has since become an important part for future plans and in developing the DLN organization.

INNOVATION FOR FUTURE BIOTECH

Several research projects have received innovation guidance through the Centre in 2018. They have been challenged on thinking innovation from an early stage in their research, and on including customers' and market needs up front. In the Lean Innovation Workshop, the participants got a clear message: The key is to understand the market and «get out of the building».

By: Åsmund H. Eikenes

– The lean innovation approach sets high demands on the researcher, says Professor Anders Goksøyr from the University of Bergen.

He heads one of the four Digital Life-projects that participated in the Lean Innovation Workshop in Oslo in October. Over two intensive days, multidisciplinary teams of five to six people brainstormed, struggled and refined the selected business ideas into shape.

– We develop an environmental diagnostics tool, explains Goksøyr.

– This workshop has given us a clearer direction for our future innovation work, and we have a tool to continue this process in the dCod-project.

CHALLENGES FOR BIOTECH

Professor Jerome Engel from UC Berkeley led the two-day workshop. Engel is an internationally recognized expert on innovation, and uses models translated and adapted to fit startups in the life sciences.

– The biggest challenge for startups, especially in biotech, is that the researchers have so much technical knowledge, says Engel.

– The science is important and complex, but the researchers are often far removed from the customers.

The workshop focused on understanding customers and the market, generating value propositions and drafting business models. Engel engaged in lively discussions with the participants to push them further along the path towards a successful startup.

THINK OF THE CUSTOMERS FIRST

– The point of this workshop is to get out of the building and engage with the marketplace, says Engel.

Careful consideration of customers and the market is a key step, and helps potential startups focus their energy towards a minimal viable product.

PhD-student Nadeem Joudeh from the University of Oslo presented results from the BEDPAN-project. They develop application-tailored nanoparticles for potential customers in the fuel cell energy and chemical catalysis industries.

– We are debating if we should sell the technology or start a company ourselves. This workshop helps me see the different options for the future, says Joudeh.

– I HAVE SHIFTED FOCUS

During the workshop, he has changed his view on what type of product he has to offer to the customers. Instead of focusing on the nanoparticles and his research, the workshop challenged him to think about the product-market fit and design a product that the customer needs.

– The engineering process and our production line is the most interesting value to the customer. I have shifted focus from what I like to do in the lab to what the market needs, concludes Joudeh.

The Centre for Digital Life Norway organized the workshop together with The Life Science Cluster, Catapult Life Science and Science for Society.

DIGITAL LIFE 2018 - TWO DAYS OF KNOWLEDGE SHARING

Around one hundred participants found their way to Bergen 20-21. March, for the annual conference of the Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2018.

The conference was held at Grand Hotel Terminus with a scientific program that covered sessions on Enzyme targeting and Engineering, Marine Biotechnology, Trust and Accountability of Science, and Synthetic Biology and Biological Engineering. Computational tools are now key in enzyme discovery and design to resolve the relationship between gene and protein sequence, protein structure and function. Spotlight was also put on how digital tools can help uncover the relationship and variation within protein superfamilies, as well as sessions on omics-technologies, CRISPR, gene editing of salmon to understand their maturation, and perspectives on synthetic biology from biochemical research.

As new technology gets integrated with society, some discussions were also dedicated to how researchers need dialogue with and trust from the public, and the goal of an open and informed debate. Professor Cameron Neylon of Australian Curtin University encouraged the audience to rethink the questions asked and the answers needed by various communities in our society. Carole Goble from the University of Manchester explained ongoing efforts in Europe and in their collaboration with DLN and ELIXIR to make FAIR data and model management and sharing feasible for the scientific community.

SUCCESSFUL POSTER SESSION

To many of the participants, the poster session was one of the conference highlights. 63 posters displayed the research projects, showcasing their research activities: What happens in the lab, in the computers and in the heads of tomorrow's researchers.

The poster session generated lively discussion as young scientists and experienced researchers got the opportunity to meet and talk about recent findings, discover new tools and develop collaborations for the future. A prize for the best poster was also duly announced: Hanne Haslene-Hox and Øystein Arlov, both from the 3DLife-project, won with their poster #41. It presented their work to develop a system for robotic handling of soft tissue engineering. *3D cell culture: Tailoring matrix properties for cell culture and high throughput screening.*

Photo: Tomasz Furmanek

INREACH AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

Last year's activities and achievements reflect the increasing momentum of the Centre and its research projects. The annual conference Digital Life 2018 was held in Bergen, with a thematic focus on enzyme engineering, marine biotech and synthetic biology, and served as a meeting point for scientific discussion and knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing for innovation was key when the Centre co-organized the innovation conference «37°C – Digitalizing Health» in Stavanger and joined the Norwegian stand at Nordic Life Science Days 2018 in Stockholm.

It is important for the Centre to be a part of societal and political discussions. One example of achieving this was when the Centre co-organized events with the Biotechnology Advisory Board and the Biozement 2.0 project, the dCod project, and the University of Oslo (UiO) during the political festival Arendalsuka 2018. We also co-presented the use of genomic data for soil improvement; «Small organism – Big Data» together with the Department of Biosciences, UiO at the yearly science festival «Forskningdagene».

The Centre's Volterra Lecture Series covered several aspects in 2018. Prof. Nikolas Rose from King's College challenged modern neuroscience and the politics of mental health. Professor Jerome Engel gave a lecture on the use of LEAN innovation in biotech in relation to a joint workshop on LEAN innovation principles. The final theme last year was the use and sharing of biomedical data by Prof. Natasa Przulj (UCL) and Prof Bonnie Berger (MIT).

In 2018, science writer Åsmund Eikenes was engaged to contribute with several pieces on the Centre's research themes, interviewing our project leaders. The work also included supporting researchers, PhD-students and postdocs, to contribute with blog-posts and dissemination of their science. Another way the Centre is supporting young scientists in their dissemination work was through sponsoring iGEM teams at NTNU and UiO, which both had great success with their projects in 2018.

THE 2ND ANNUAL CONFERENCE OF DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY RESEARCH SCHOOL

Dressed in appropriate attire for the Viking feast during the 2nd annual conference of Digital Life Norway Research School

Photo: Liv Eggset Falkenberg

Organized for and by the members, the annual conference is the most important event of the Research School. In 2018, it took place 29. May- 1. June at Stiklestad, outside Trondheim. 70 PhD students and postdocs from all over Norway participated, and enjoyed excellent scientific talks as well as social activities outside in the sun.

The topics of the conference were «Scientific communication: How to present your research», and «The future: Will your research make an impact?». All participants presented their scientific work or projects in highly interdisciplinary groups, which gave them an extra challenge in terms of presentation skills. Tia Tidwell from the University of Stavanger took home the prize for the best scientific image. Big thanks to Agnieszka Gawin, Nina Bjørk Arnfinnsdottir, and Maria Bårdsen Hesjedal, all from NTNU, for their efforts in organizing the conference.

OTHER EVENTS

The Research School offers travel grants for members who wants to attend courses and events outside their hometown, and in 2018, 23 such events were available to the members. In addition to scientific courses, the Research School also gives popular generic courses, such as scientific writing and illustration workshops. The first «Science, technology, and society: RRI course Digital Life Norway» was held in 2018, contributing to the focus on responsible thinking in young researchers.

NEW BOARD MEMBERS IN 2018

Bjørn Olav Brandsdal (UiT), Emil Karlsen (NTNU), Eva Lena F. Estensmo (UiO), Roland Sauter (UiT), Shirin Fallahi (UiB) and Gunhild Fjeld (UIS).

We encourage everyone in the centre to keep updated on our offers through our newsletters or our website: www.digitallifenorway.org/dlnrs

SPARKING A SCIENTIFIC CAREER IN THE CENTRE FOR DIGITAL LIFE

Through the research projects, the Centre constitutes a number of PhD candidates. They are given the chance to grow academically and scientifically through several courses, workshops and conferences. Here, two of them tell about their research and how they have made use of the Centre this far in their career.

MARTE JENSSEN

UiT – the Arctic University of Norway
PhD candidate in the DigiBiotics project

– I am working in the DigiBiotics project. My part of the project is the actual biodiscovery part, trying to isolate antibacterial compounds produced by marine microorganisms. We have had several microorganisms whole genome sequenced, so I am also interested in the genome mining approach to finding antibacterial compounds. It is a very interesting and exciting project that I am happy to be a part of!

For me, the Research School and the Centre provide a lot of interesting opportunities like conferences and courses. I attended the 2nd annual conference of the Research School in Stiklestad in 2018, and really enjoyed it. It was actually so interesting that I am part of the scientific committee for the conference in 2019.

EMIL KARLSEN

NTNU
PhD candidate in the BioZement 2.0 project

– I am a systems biologist working on genome-scale metabolic modeling of bacterial metabolism in the research project BioZement 2.0. We try to design an alternative, more environmentally friendly, process for the production of concrete, that uses bacteria. In my daily work, I try to make sense of large amounts of biological data by capturing it in models and testing for consistency, before using these models for analysis and simulation.

Apart from being funded by the Centre for Digital Life Norway, I have benefited greatly from the courses offered by the Research School. They have not only improved my understanding of biological phenomena on the microscale, but also of interactions between science and society on the macroscale.

THE DIGITAL LIFE YEAR AT A GLANCE

MEMBERS DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY RESEARCH SCHOOL

DLN RESEARCH SCHOOL MEMBERSHIP BY UNIVERSITY

FINANCING DLN 2018

60%
more members

COLLABORATION

IP AND COMMERCIALIZATION

* Total number of Digital Life research projects was respectively 11 in 2017 and 17 in 2018.

NUMBER OF POTENTIAL BUSINESS IDEAS

* Total number of Digital Life research projects was respectively 11 in 2017 and 17 in 2018.

NEW BOARD MEMBERS IN 2018

Arne Smalås
Dean of the Faculty of Science and Technology at the University of Tromsø.

He represents the DLN node partners on the board.

Emilie Lasson
Chief Commercial Officer in Genetic Analysis AS.

She replaces Silviya Seres as one of the industry representatives on the board.

THE COORDINATORS OF CENTRE FOR DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY

The governance and networking part of the Centre for Digital Life is run by coordinators at the three hub-partners NTNU and the Universities of Oslo and Bergen. They oversee the day-to-day operations. The Centre Leader and Centre Coordinator manage the Centre in close collaboration with the leaders and coordinators in the different work groups. The work groups correspond to six different focus areas: governance, responsible research and innovation (RRI), innovation and industry involvement, training and recruitment (including the DLN Research School), competence and infrastructure network, and communication.

The coordinators, their affiliation and areas of responsibility are:

Marie Hjelmseth Aune
NTNU
Centre Coordinator

Rune Kleppe
UiB
Competence and Infrastructure Management

Alexandra Patriksson
UiO
Innovation and Industry Involvement

Liv Falkenberg
NTNU
Training and Recruitment

Raffael Himmelsbach
NTNU
Responsible Research and Innovation

Hilde Zwaig Kolstad
UiO
Communication

Brage Hansen
NTNU
Administrative Support

DIGITAL LIFE NORWAY

Kjemi 3, 3.329,
Sem Sælandsvei 6
N-7491 Trondheim

www.digitallifenorway.com

